

THE ROLE OF PROFITABILITY IN THE FIRM VALUE MODEL (EMPIRICAL STUDY ON FOOD AND BEVERAGE COMPANIES)

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Abstract

The purpose of the study is to conduct an analysis and answer the research gap that occurs among researchers and the phenomenon that occurs where Firm value is a problem that needs to be researched using ROA as an intervening variable. This type of research is quantitative descriptive with multiple regression analysis method of panel data using the research object of food and beverage sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange. By using the purposive sampling method, the number of cross sections obtained was ten companies that were observed in this study and with a time series for 5 years. Furthermore, this study produces the maximization of Firm value through profitability, ROA. This study uses an approach of two research models that are integrated into one and each through the stages of model selection testing, namely the Chow Test, Hausman Test and Lagrange Multiplier Tests. The results of the study on the first model using the endogenous variable ROA, apart from TATO and Sales Growth, all exogenous variables can explain their influence significantly on ROA with the highest level of sensitivity in the Leverage variable. The results of the second model study using Firm value as an endogenous variable are that in addition to TATO and Current Ratio, all exogenous variables can significantly explain their influence on Firm value with the highest level of sensitivity in the Leverage variable. These results are expected to help as a guideline for public companies to obtain market appreciation that is proxied into Firm value.

Keywords: Firm Size, Leverage, TATO, Current Ratio, Sales Growth, ROA, Firm Value.

1. INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

A company has a specific purpose for its owner. The purpose is to obtain maximum profit or the greatest possible profit from its operational activities in the short term. And the second purpose is the main purpose of the company, namely prosperity for the company owners or shareholders by maximizing the company's value as reflected in the company's stock price. This second purpose is a long-term goal, Harjito & Martono (2011).

A company's value is a condition that has occurred and been achieved by the company, which is related to the company's success as a picture of public trust in this case investors in the company. The success of the company is measured by firm value, which can be measured through the company's stock market price. The company's stock market price is reflected in the overall investor assessment of each equity owned by the company. According to Bringham Houston, the high value of the company will also be followed by high prosperity for its shareholders (investors). Firm value will provide maximum prosperity for shareholders if the stock price increases (increases). The higher or higher the stock price of a company, the higher the firm value. If the value can be proxied by the stock price, then maximizing the company's

market value is the same as maximizing the stock market price, Harjito & Martono (2011). According to Moeheriono (2014), performance is the achievement of results or the degree of accomplishment, or work achievement or performance. In other words, performance is a record of the results obtained from certain job functions or activities during a certain period of time. Performance assessment can be used as a measure of the success of an organization over a certain period of time. The assessment can be used as input for improving or increasing the organization's performance in the future.

Robert S. Kaplan and David P. Norton in Moeheriono (2014), one way a company's financial performance is measured is financial. Financial is built from a study of performance measurement in the business sector, so what is meant by financial is related to financial sustainability. This financial performance is used by shareholders in order to assess the performance of the organization (company). In other words, the organization must meet the expectations of shareholders in order to be considered successful by shareholders.

In Fahmi (2018) financial performance is an analysis carried out to see the extent to which a company has implemented using financial implementation rules properly and correctly. Good company financial performance is the implementation of applicable rules that have been carried out properly and correctly. Company performance is identical to company profit. So the main focus of financial reporting is to provide information on the company's (operational) performance, which is a measurement of profit and its components. Because company performance is identical to company profit, it is hereinafter referred to as profitability which uses Return on Assets (ROA). Investors, creditors, and other users who want to know the company's prospects in obtaining net cash flow are parties who are specifically interested in this information, Suwaldiman (2015).

In Hayati, et al. (2017), who conducted a study on 10 food and beverage companies on the Indonesia Stock Exchange in the period 2012 - 2014 with that Company Size has a positive and significant effect on Return on Assets. In another study, Dewi & Candradewi (2018), using the research object of 11 Investment Companies on the Indonesia Stock Exchange for the period 2013 - 2016, with the result that Company Size has a positive and significant effect on Company Financial Performance. The same result by Krisdamayanti & Retnan, (2020), with the result that Company Size has a positive and significant effect on Company Financial Performance. Also in Chandra, et al. (2020), Company Size has a positive and significant effect on Return on Assets. Different research results by Fauzi & Puspitasari (2021) state that company size has a negative and significant effect on company financial performance.

Other research by Nopitasari, et al. (2017), that Leverage has a positive and significant effect on Company Performance, Different results by Purushothaman, et al. (2022), Azis & Hartono (2017), where Leverage has a negative and significant effect on Company Financial Performance. Very different results by Enekwe, et al. (2014), Raza (2013), where the results of their research are that Leverage has no significant effect on profitability. Hayati, et al. (2017), Abbas (2017), Chandra, et al. (2020), Firmansyah, et al. (2022), where the results of their research show that TATO has a positive and significant effect on Return on Assets

Profitability. Different results are shown by Widjayanti & Aslamiyah (2024), that TATO has no significant effect on Return on Assets profitability.

In Abbas (2017), Utama & Muid (2014), Zarkasyi, et al. (2021), Amanda (2019), also produced research that Current Ratio has a positive and significant effect on Return On Asset profitability. Different results were shown by Ulzanah & Murtaqi (2015), that Current Ratio has a negative and significant effect on Return on Asset profitability. While very different results were produced by Chandra, et al. (2020), that Current Ratio has an insignificant effect on Return on Asset. In further research by Prakasiwi, et al. (2019), Cahyana & Suhendah (2020), with the results that Sales Growth has a negative and significant effect on the Company's Financial Performance. Different results were carried out by Oladipupo & Azeez (2022), Arisudhana (2023), with the results that Sales Growth has a positive and significant effect on the Company's Financial Performance. Meanwhile, very different research results were conducted by Putra & Badjra (2015), that Sales Growth has an insignificant effect on Profitability.

Various research results on firm value were conducted by Soge & Brata (2020), Prasetyorini (2013), Lambey, et al. (2021), Yuwono & Aurelia (2021), Zurriaha & Sembiring (2020), that company size has a significant effect and is positively correlated with firm value, but different results were produced by Halfiyah & Suriawinata (2019), Emanuel & Rasyid (2019), Umam & Halimah (2021), where the results of their research were that Company Size has a significant effect with a negative correlation to firm value. From other variables on firm value, it was produced in Farooq & Masood (2016), Gill & Obradovich (2012), Nugraha & Alfaris (2020), that Leverage has a significant effect with a positive correlation on firm value, but different from the research results of Sujoko & Soebiantoro (2007), Soge & Brata (2020), that Leverage has a significant effect with a negative correlation on firm value.

Other research results on firm value using the exogenous variable TATO have been conducted by Simorangkir (2019), Vedy & Santoso (2022), Kahfi, et al. (2018), Ulfah & Abbas (2020), Nafisah, et al. (2018), that the results of their research show that TATO has a significant effect on firm value with a positive correlation. In Dewi & Sembiring (2022), Sihotang & Hutabarat (2020), Rudini, et al. (2021), Nafisah, et al. (2018), Kahfi, et al. (2018), they have conducted research on firm value using the exogenous variable current ratio which resulted in the Current Ratio having a significant effect and being positively correlated to firm value. The use of other exogenous variables, sales growth has been carried out by Khoeriyah (2020), Fajriah, et al. (2022), Sulastri, et al. (2023), Febriyanto (2018), where the results of their research show that Sales Growth has a significant effect and is positively correlated to firm value, but there are different research results in Emanuel & Rasyid (2019), that Sales Growth has a significant effect and is negatively correlated to firm value. Further research developments using the exogenous variable profitability Return On Assets conducted by Halimah & Komariah (2017), Sianturi (2015), Ulfa & Asyik (2018), Syardiana, et al. (2015), where the results of their study explain that Profitability Return On Assets has a significant effect with a positive correlation to firm value, but different results are shown by Yuditia & Suhaedi (2024), that Profitability Return On Assets has an insignificant effect on firm value. Seeing the results of research from

various parties that are not as explained in the paragraph above, it encourages researchers to do re-testing.

2. HYPOTHESIS

- H1: Firm Size (SIZE) influences Return On Assets (ROA).
- H2: There is an influence of Leverage (LEV) on Return On Assets (ROA).
- H3: That there is an influence of Total Asset Turn Over (TATO) on Return On Assets (ROA)
- H4: There is an influence of Currant Ratio (CR) on Return On Assets (ROA)
- H5: There is an influence of Sales Growth (SG) on Return On Assets (ROA)
- H6: There is an influence of Firm Size (SIZE) on Firm Value (NP).
- H7: There is an influence of Leverage (LEV) on Firm Value (NP).
- H8: There is an influence of Total Asset Turn Over (TATO) on Firm Value (NP).
- H9: There is an influence of Current Ratio (CR) on Firm Value (NP)
- H10: There is an influence of Sales Growth (SG) on Firm Value (NP)
- H11: There is an influence of Return on Assets (ROA) on Firm Value (NP)

Figure 1: Research Framework

3. RESEARCH METHODS

This study uses a quantitative descriptive approach with the analysis method used is multiple linear regression of panel data using a combination of five-year time series data or the period 2017 - 2021 or 5 years and a cross section of 10 selected companies as research samples. This

study uses objects of Food and Beverage companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange with a population of all companies listed in the Food and Beverage sector.

Operational Variables:

Table 1: Operational Variables

No	Variables	Notation	Formulas
1	Firm Size	SIZE it	Log Total Assets
2	Leverage	LEV it	$\frac{\text{Debt}}{\text{Equity}}$
3	Total Asset Turn Over	TATO it	$\frac{\text{Revenue}}{\text{Total Assets}}$
4	Current Ratio	CR it	$\frac{\text{Current Assets}_{it}}{\text{Current Liabilities}_{it}}$
5	Sales Growth	SG it	$\frac{\text{Sales}_{it} - \text{Sales}_{i(t-1)}}{\text{Sales}_{i(t-1)}}$
6	Return on Asset	ROA it	$\frac{\text{Earnings After Tax}}{\text{Total Assets}}$
7	Firm Value (Tobin's Q)	NP it	$\frac{\text{MVE} + \text{D}}{\text{TA}}$

Panel Data Multiple Regression Estimation

In conducting multiple regression estimation of panel data, it is first ensured that there is a combination of time series data and cross-section data. The approach that can be taken in conducting the analysis between time series data and cross-section data can use the following analysis:

1. Common Effect Model (CEM)
2. Fixed Effect Model (FEM)
3. Random Effect Model (REM)

Model Selection in Testing

The three basic analyses above are used to carry out model suitability testing procedures in order to select the appropriate panel data multiple regression model in the following ways:

Chow Test

F-statistic as a standard used to determine the choice between the Common Effect model or the Fixed Effect model. Acceptance or rejection of the hypothesis is based on the level of $\alpha = 5\%$ on the null hypothesis (H_0) and the alternative hypothesis (H_a). Each of the two models above will technically compare the calculation of the F-statistic with the F-table. The results of the F count <from the F table will reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and vice versa will accept the alternative hypothesis (H_a). Thus the appropriate model to be used is the Fixed Effect Model, the decision will be taken otherwise if the results will be different.

Hausman Test

In the direction of Hausman testing, it is intended to determine the choice of Fixed Effect Model or Random Effect Model. The criteria used are the Chi-Square statistical distribution and degree of freedom as much as k with the number of exogenous variables as the basis for testing.

The test will result in accepting the null hypothesis (H₀) and rejecting the alternative hypothesis (H_a) for the next model will be said to be fit and use the Random Effect Model, but on the contrary will use the Fixed Effect Model if the statistical hypothesis rejects the null hypothesis (H₀) and accepts the alternative hypothesis (H_a).

Lagrange Multiplier Test (LM)

To determine the fit model in Lagrange Multiplier (LM) through the selection process between the Common Effect Model or Random Effect Model. The basis of the test uses the Chi-Squares distribution with a degree of freedom equal to the number of exogenous variables.

If the result of the LM statistic value is greater than the critical value of the Chi-Squares statistic, it will reject the null hypothesis (H₀) and accept the alternative hypothesis (H_a), so it means that the fit estimate to use is the Random Effect Model. Conversely, if the LM statistic value is smaller than the critical value of the Chi-Squares statistic, it will accept the null hypothesis (H₀) and reject the alternative hypothesis (H_a), this means that the use of the Common Effect Model is more appropriate.

Panel Data Regression Model

Structural Equation of Research Model I,

$$ROA_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 SIZE_{it} + \beta_2 LEV_{it} + \beta_3 TATO_{it} + \beta_4 CR_{it} + \beta_5 SG_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

i = 1,2,....., N ; t = 1,2,.....T

Structural Equation of Research Model II,

$$NP_{it} = \alpha + \beta_1 SIZE_{it} + \beta_2 LEV_{it} + \beta_3 TATO_{it} + \beta_4 CR_{it} + \beta_5 SG_{it} + \beta_6 ROA_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

i = 1,2,....., N ; t = 1,2,.....,T

Where:

SIZE	=	Firm Size		ε	=	Error component
LEV	=	Leverage		β	=	Slope
TATO	=	Total Asset Turn Over		α	=	Intercept
CR	=	Current Ratio		N	=	Number of Observations
SG	=	Sales Growth		T	=	Lots of time
ROA	=	Return On Assets		NxT	=	Number of Panel Data
NP	=	Firm Value (Tobin's Q)				

4. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Results

Descriptive Statistics and Model Fit Test

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	SIZE	LEV	TATO	CR	SG	ROA	NP
Mean	12.71056	0.365311	118.6053	297.7829	7.442377	8.867370	2.133098
Median	12.57646	0.354390	96.44650	239.4691	5.362880	7.819669	2.138125
Maximum	14.25372	0.638523	315.7465	863.7842	47.46841	22.28743	3.967017
Minimum	11.76115	0.140557	44.57775	100.3156	-20.42230	1.267096	0.826625
Std. Dev.	0.740332	0.148256	68.31854	190.6270	11.36131	5.356761	0.989223
Skewness	0.657097	-0.064701	1.408169	1.299158	0.533243	0.697089	0.156659
Kurtosis	2.239638	1.678730	4.547709	4.186942	5.092962	2.963286	1.841394
Jarque-Bera	4.802613	3.671877	21.51492	17.00015	11.49559	4.052255	3.001118
Probability	0.090600	0.159464	0.000021	0.000203	0.003190	0.131845	0.223006
Sum	635.5278	18.26556	5930.266	14889.15	372.1188	443.3685	106.6549
Sum Sq. Dev.	26.85645	1.077009	228703.7	1780594.	6324.890	1406.049	47.94956
Observations	50	50	50	50	50	50	50

Source: Processed data

Return on Assets and Firm Value as Endogenous Variables in the Suitability Testing of Research Models 1 & 2.

Table 3: Chow Tests

Research Model 1 Common Effect Vs Fixed Effect Endogenous Variable: Return on Assets				Research Model 2 Common Effect Vs Fixed Effect Endogenous Variable: Firm Value			
Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.	Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	3.154067	(9,35)	0.0069	Cross-section F	20.510523	(9,34)	0.0000
Cross-section Chi-square	29.695221	9	0.0005	Cross-section Chi-square	93.042941	9	0.0000

Source: Processed data

The test results of the Chow-test in Research Model 1 and Research Model 2 produce statistical hypotheses: rejecting the null hypothesis (H_0) and accepting the alternative hypothesis (H_a) at the level of $\alpha = 5\%$. It can be said that the Fixed Effect Model is more appropriate to use than the Common Effect Model. (Table-3)

Table 4: Hausman Tests

Research Model 1 Fixed Effect Vs Random Effect Endogenous Variable: Return on Assets				Research Model 2 Fixed Effect Vs Random Effect Endogenous Variable: Firm Value			
Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.	Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	8.327253	5	0.1391	Cross-section random	9.369944	6	0.1538

Source: Processed data

The results of the Hausman-test in Research Model 1 and Research Model 2 produce statistical hypotheses: accepting the null hypothesis (H_0) and rejecting the alternative hypothesis (H_a) at the level of $\alpha = 5\%$. This can be interpreted that the Random Effect Model is more appropriate to use than the Fixed Effect Model. (Table-4)

Table 5: Lagrange Multiplier Tests

Research Model 1 Common Effect Vs Random Effect Endogenous Variable: Return on Assets				Research Model 2 Common Effect Vs Random Effect Endogenous Variable: Firm Value			
Test Hypothesis				Test Hypothesis			
Test Summary	Cross-section	Time	Both	Test Summary	Cross-section	Time	Both
Breusch-Pagan	5.035409 (0.0248)	0.230813 (0.6309)	5.26622(0.0217)	Breusch-Pagan	39.26178 (0.0000)	1.404458 (0.2360)	40.6662 (0.0000)

Source: Processed data

The results of the Lagrange Multiplier Tests in Research Model 1 and Research Model 2 produce statistical hypotheses: rejecting the null hypothesis (H_0) and accepting the alternative hypothesis (H_a) at the level of $\alpha = 5\%$. This can be interpreted that the Random Effect Model is more appropriate to use than the Common Effect Model. (Table-5).

**Table 6: Endogenous Variable: ROA
Total pool (balanced) observations: 50**

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-13.11029	11.64871	-1.125471	0.2665
SIZE	1.563685	0.670768	2.331187	0.0244
LEV	-9.411959	3.986960	-2.360685	0.0227
TATO	0.004074	0.011968	0.340414	0.7352
CR	0.015722	0.003808	4.128309	0.0002
SG	0.050494	0.042567	1.186235	0.2419
Adjusted R-squared	0.426295			
F-statistic	8.281963; Prob(F-statistic) : 0.000014			

Source: Processed data

**Table 7: Endogenous Variable: NP
Total pool (balanced) observations: 50**

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	15.92249	5.326644	2.989215	0.0046
SIZE	-1.002087	0.440952	-2.272556	0.0281
LEV	-2.716867	1.070101	-2.538888	0.0148
TATO	0.000540	0.002436	0.221536	0.8257
CR	-0.002195	0.001371	-1.600460	0.1168
SG	-0.009598	0.003308	-2.901356	0.0058
ROA	0.067801	0.014971	4.528820	0.0000
Adjusted R-squared	0.421312			
F-statistic	6.945711; Prob(F-statistic) : 0.000033			

Source: Processed data

- 1) Firm Size significantly affects ROA Profitability with a positive correlation (Table 6).
- 2) Capital Structure/ Leverage significantly affects and negatively correlates with ROA Profitability (Table 6).
- 3) Total Assets Turn Over / TATO has an insignificant effect on ROA Profitability (Table 6).
- 4) Liquidity / Current Ratio significantly affects ROA Profitability with a positive correlation (Table 6).
- 5) Sales Growth has an insignificant effect on ROA Profitability (Table 6).
- 6) Firm Size significantly affects Firm Value / Tobin's Q with a negative correlation (Table 7).
- 7) Capital Structure / Leverage significantly affects and negatively correlates with Firm Value / Tobin's Q (Table 7).
- 8) Total Assets Turn Over / TATO has an insignificant effect on Firm Value/Tobin's Q (Table 7).
- 9) Liquidity / Current Ratio has an insignificant effect on Firm Value / Tobin's Q (Table 7).
- 10) Sales Growth has a significant effect on Firm Value / Tobin's Q with a negative correlation (Table 7).
- 11) Profitability / ROA has a significant effect on Firm Value / Tobin's Q with a positive correlation (Table 7).

B. Discussion

In the results of this study, the endogenous variable used is profitability which is proxied into Return On Assets (ROA) in the first research model where the results are that apart from the exogenous variables Total Assets Turn Over and Sales Growth, all exogenous variables used can explain their influence on ROA with the highest sensitivity level being in the leverage variable. The results of the study in the second research model, only the exogenous variable Total Assets Turn Over cannot explain its influence on the endogenous variable Firm Value which is proxied into Tobin's Q with the highest sensitivity level being in the leverage variable

or the same as in the results of the first model study. The intervening variable Return On Assets (ROA) used in this study can function to mediate the influence of exogenous variables on the endogenous variable Firm Value / Tobin's Q. Thus, the market reaction that contributes to firm value will depend on ROA in companies in the Food and Beverage sector.

5. CONCLUSION

Findings: The results of this study conclude that Return on Assets (ROA) as an intervening variable has a significant effect on firm value, which means that market reaction as part of Tobin's Q will depend on ROA. In addition, among the exogenous variables used and the highest level of sensitivity is the leverage variable. This is also a suggestion for further researchers and especially for company management authorities regarding the importance of paying attention to the leverage variable as a key variable by capital market players in the Food and Beverage sector on the Indonesia Stock Exchange.

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